

Developer Activity Survey

We are researchers in [company name] investigating how much time developers spend in different activities. The answers to this survey will enable us to best focus our research on developer tools and processes to help developers in their daily tasks.

We would be greatly appreciative if you would be willing to answer the following questions. The survey shouldn't take more than 5-10 minutes. Thank you.

This survey is completely anonymous and all questions are optional. No personal information will be collected. Only aggregated data will be shared with [company name] collaborators. If you have any questions or if you'd rather not participate and want no further contact, please email [researcher email address].

Other than some initial demographic questions, many of the questions in this survey ask you how much time to spent on various tasks yesterday. To be consistent, **we ask for all answers in the form of minutes**. We made this decision not because we're interested in accuracy down to the minute, but because we found it easier for respondents to write fractions of an hour in minutes rather than decimals of an hour (indicating 10 minutes in decimal of an hour is not easy). Some questions in the survey ask about what occurred "yesterday". If you did not work yesterday (took the day off, it was a weekend, etc.), please answer for the most recent day that you worked full time.

Demographic Information

1. How many years have you worked in software development?
[text field]
2. Which of the following best describes your job role?
[radio boxes with selection, options omitted for double blind review]
3. Which of the following best characterizes the environment you worked in yesterday?
 - o Private Office
 - o Shared Office
 - o Cubicle
 - o Open/Shared workspace
 - o Remote
 - o Other: [textbox]

Time Spent at Work

4. Consider your day yesterday. In the table below, please enter in roughly how many minutes you spent in each of the activities.

If you did not work yesterday (took the day off, it was a weekend, etc.), please answer for the most recent day that you worked full time.

You may find it useful to consult your email (both sent and received) or look at your calendar to jog your memory. If yesterday was unusual (e.g. you had a doctor's appointment, an off-site meeting, or worked from home), please still respond regarding your day as it happened. Please just try to remember roughly how much time you spent in each activity. If you worked outside of "normal" hours, please include that as well.

	Minutes spent
Writing Code	[textbox]
Debugging or fixing bugs	
Running tests on code	
Meetings	
Email	
Helping/Mentoring	
Working on/with specs/requirements	
Reviewing code	
Documentation	
Honing skills/Continuous learning	
Breaks/Lunch	
Administrative tasks	
Networking/Maintaining relationships	
Interruptions	
Travel	

If there is an activity that you think should be included, please enter it in one of the blank rows at the bottom of the table.

If you have feedback about this question (ways to improve it, things that are unclear, etc.), please do your best to fill in the table and provide the feedback in the next question.

[textbox]

Typical and Good Workdays

5. Was yesterday typical?

yes

no

If not, why?

[textbox]

6. Would you consider yesterday a good day? Why or why not?

[textbox]

7. Do you distinguish between writing code, writing tests, and debugging?

yes

no

Meetings and Interruptions

8. Roughly how many times were you interrupted yesterday?

[textbox]

9. After you were interrupted yesterday, how many minutes on average did it take to get back to being focused on the task that was interrupted?

[textbox]

10. Yesterday, what percentage of your time was spent in meetings or preparing for meetings?

(enter percentage)

[textbox]

11. Yesterday, how many unplanned meetings did you have?

[textbox]

Approximately how many minutes did these unplanned meetings take up in total?

[textbox]

12. What percentage of your meetings yesterday did you find useful?

[textbox]

13. How many impromptu sync-ups did you have yesterday? (please enter a number)

[textbox]

14. Yesterday, what was the longest period of time that you were able to code for? (please enter minutes)

[textbox]